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Parental Sexuality Education As Predictors Of Sexual Behaviour Among Adolescent Female Students In Osun State Public Secondary Schools, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of parental sexuality education on the sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and data were collected from 750 participants selected through a multistage sampling procedure across 15 schools. A self-developed and validated instrument titled "Parental Sexuality Education and Adolescent Sexual Behaviour-Survey, was administered electronically via Google Forms. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and linear regression at the 0.05 significance level. Results revealed a notable prevalence of sexual behaviours among respondents, including exposure of sensitive body parts 253 (33.7%), regular sexual intercourse 177 (23.6%), and contraceptive use 168 (22.4%). Findings also showed that 441 (58.8%) participants moderately rated the sexuality education they received from parents. Results further showed that parental sexuality education exerted significant influence in psychosocial domains, including enhancing self-esteem and confidence ($1.6691 \pm .5875$), strengthening resistance to peer pressure and unhealthy relationships ($1.7392 \pm .6102$), fostering informed decision-making (1.1453 ± 0.2351), and dispelling myths about sexuality ($1.9390 \pm .8985$). However, its influence was minimal on behavioural sexual pattern such as delaying sexual initiation ($0.0430 \pm .0206$), discouraging indecent exposure ($0.0115 \pm .0321$), reducing risky sexual practices ($0.1029 \pm .0263$), and decreasing contraceptive use ($0.0041 \pm .0002$). The study concluded that while parental sexuality education was effective in shaping adolescents' attitudes and knowledge, it exhibited no significant association with the sexual behavioural patterns of female students in Osun State public secondary schools. It was recommended among others the establishment of health and sexuality counselling units in all public secondary schools to address adolescents' sexual behavioural patterns comprehensively.

Keywords: Adolescent Female Students, Parental Sexuality Education, Sexuality, Sexual Behaviour

Introduction

Adolescence marks the stage of development that exists between childhood and adulthood. During adolescence, individuals are faced with numerous physical, social and emotional changes. The challenge for adolescent female is the emergence of secondary sexual features. Adolescent females will begin to develop breasts and pubic hair, and experience other changes including, an increase in height and widening in hips. Along with these changes, comes the emergence of sexual feelings and curiosity that accompany this stage of development. The emergence of sexual feelings and curiosity is a result of hormonal changes that occur during puberty (Olawale, 2021). This is the stage where adolescent females begin to formulate their sexual and gender identities. Many adolescent females do not have access to accurate and age-appropriate information on sexuality. In many African societies, including Nigeria, discussions about sexual matters are not typically transparent and openly discussed because of social and cultural restraints. Therefore many adolescent females turn to friends, social media, or pornography to fulfill their curiosity, which may lead to misconceptions and risky sexual practices (Olawale, 2021; Olubayo-Fatiregun, 2024; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2022).

Young people's sexual behaviour has undergone intense scrutiny in recent years. Current Nigerian customs and norms are substantially transforming when compared to several decades ago and these changes have also affected the sexual behaviour of the females. Sexual behaviour is defined as any behaviour engaged in by two people or a group of people that produces sexual arousal. It is any behaviour that increases the likelihood of a person engaging in sexual behaviours with another person (Olubayo-Fatiregun, 2024). Thus, sexual behaviour refers to any behaviour motivated by a sexual feeling, desire, or sexual gratification whether it is reproductive or not (U.S. Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, 2018). Sexual behaviour can be classified, based on the number and sex of the students, into solitary behaviour; socio-sexual behaviour; and homosexual (Paul, 2022). In most cases, sexual behaviour includes an exceptionally broad range of activities an individual engages in to express their sexuality including sexual practices, sexual relationships, reproductive health, sexually

transmitted infections (STIs), and contraception (World Health Organisation (WHO, 2019). The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (2021), reports sexual behaviours increase the risk of infecting or passing on viruses or increase the possibility of unintended pregnancy. Adolescent females engage in sexual behaviours that include multiple sexual partners, regular changes in sexual partners, and oral sex (Joe, 2018). As well, the adolescent females engaged in risky sexual behaviours that included anal sexual intercourse without a condom, unreliable methods of birth control, and unprotected sexual intercourse (Olawale, 2021).

Internationally, in 2020, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reported that 20% of all new HIV diagnosis, and more than half of the nearly 20 million new STIs were amongst young females (aged 15-24 years). Also, more than 145,000 infants were born to adolescent females in 2021. Moreover, an estimated 14,000 new HIV infections occurred each day as a result of risky sexual behaviour more than 95% of which are in developing countries (CDC, 2022; World Health Organization (WHO), 2017), with many of these infections occurring in sub-Saharan Africa. Lastly, HIV/AIDS and unintended pregnancies remain two leading causes of mortality and morbidity amongst adolescent females worldwide (Wusu, 2023; WHO, 2017; Yepoyan, 2014).

Studies across the continent of Africa have documented that adolescent females in sub-Saharan Africa are entering sexual activity at an alarming rate, with as many as 71.7% (depending on the country), or in some countries such as Angola, Benin, Burkina Faso, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau and Sudan (WHO, 2015; WHO, 2019). Nigeria has one of the highest rates of HIV in the world, especially among adolescent girls and young women aged 15–24. There are generally many parents who feel they lack the skills, or the comfort to discuss sexuality with their children. Furthermore, there are certain cultural norms that inhibit those conversations, therefore placing itself in a position of silence which ultimately cultivates curiosity, secrecy, and harmful decision making with adolescents. Studies have shown that parents, especially mothers, can provide their daughters with knowledge and communication skills to assist them through difficult decisions. The significance of parental involvement in the sexual education of adolescents' particularly adolescent girls, can guide them to make better informed and responsible decisions concerning their sexual health choices (United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2019). Furthermore, in Ghana, it was mentioned that one in three female adolescents in slums have ever had sexual intercourse and the majority of girls who have had sexual intercourse are those who are not in school. Evidence indicates that approximately one-third of adolescents who had initiated sexual activity reported that their first sexual encounter was unplanned. This phenomenon is further compounded by the sociocultural context of Ethiopia, where discourse on sexual and reproductive health remains a highly sensitive subject and is infrequently addressed in open communication (United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), 2021). In Osun State, a report showed that 19.2% of in-school adolescents engage in risky sexual behaviours, moderated by personal predictors, such as age, gender, attitude, perception, and self-image (Fatusi, 2024). The report goes on to state that, the percentage of condom use among females aged 15–24 years, while engaging in high-risk sex were extremely important in Osun State. Furthermore, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2022), argued that, more than 76% of females had their first sexual experience before age 16, and 34% had had more than two partners. Fatusi (2024), reiterated that risky sexual behaviours such as early sexual debut, not using condoms or using them incorrectly, having multiple sexual partners, put females at risk for acquiring sexually transmitted infections (STIs), as well as increasing the odds of an unintended adolescent pregnancy.

Multiple studies suggested that sex education should not leave it up to the school and must involve parents as well. A study of parents advising adolescents about sex education in New Brunswick, Canada, found 95% agreed sex education responsibility should be shared by the school and the parents (Samuel, 2010; Tefera, & Mulatie, 2014; United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, 2021; and World Health Organization, 2017). United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (2021), pointed out, sexuality education in the home was available in most African countries only during initiation rites and ceremonies which advise girls with information on how to sleep with their husbands, menstrual taboos, how to recognize pregnancy, and to keep clean in the case of personal. This information used has not helped or decreased the sexual behaviour risky choices of adolescent females. Rather adolescents are engaged in risky sexual relationships with ill-informed choices (prostitution, sugar daddies, protection in exchange for sexual favours in street gangs and so on). The fact that parents or the educational system seem to be incapable of dealing with this issue; it appears that youth makes a choice to view their peers, social media, or popular role models, who also failed to provide the necessary information or morale for a healthy education of adolescent sexuality (Olawale, 2021). Olubayo-Fatiregun, Ayodele & Adebero (2017), also found that, Nigerian youths are now more both daring and assertive about their sexuality, and less value is attached to virginity. However, the only solution to this challenge is to involve parents to take the responsibilities of educating adolescent females on the need to live a healthy life and maintain respected relationship with the opposite sex. In her submission, Olubayo-Fatiregun (2024), viewed that, teaching sexuality at home could be very tough for most parents.

Parents should be the primary sex educators of their children. She said that, mothers are considered to be the most ideal person to give sex education at home due to familiarity, and closeness.

Similarly, sexuality education in the home, according to WHO (2015), allows youths the opportunity to quickly acclimate to the norms, values, beliefs and ideas they will need in making their own healthy relationships. Olubayo-Fatiregun (2012), noted that the role of parents' in sex education is the greatest during the adolescent year. The findings also showed that, parental understanding of social, psychological, and sexual issues in this problematic phase of life for youths can assist them in cognizing that adolescence stage is a normal stage of life, making it easier for them to adjust accordingly. This non-involvement can also lead to misunderstanding, heightened curiosity, and secret sexual behaviour in adolescent girls' lives. Moreover, cultural and religious beliefs often serve to dissuade parents from avoiding these communication opportunities, which can lead to a readiness in young females engaging in sexual decisions. If young females are allowed to manoeuvre decisions without parents' advice and expertise, Olubayo-Fatiregun (2024), suggested that adolescent girls may develop a standard pattern risky sexual behaviours including unprotected sex with future health implications.

Addressing this issue requires a higher parental role in education on sexuality and equipping parents with content knowledge and communication skills to effectively support their daughters when having discussions on sex and relationships. In her take home message, Olubayo-Fatiregun (2024), charged all educational institutions and community organizations to fully engage with parents as partners in providing training and resources that would facilitate healthy sexual and relational discussions on sex and relationships. Wusu (2023), added that parents ought to be advocates by encouraging discourse and the need for parents to have judgment-free discussions as paramount to assist and empower adolescent females with accurate information for responsible decision making in sexual health. The provision of parental sexual health education would promote societies with desirable social consequences of reducing risky sexual behaviours in adolescent females, leading to advancing their physical, emotional, and social wellbeing. The persistence of unplanned sexual debut among adolescent females, coupled with the prevailing sociocultural sensitivities that hinder open discussions on sexual and reproductive health in Ethiopia, highlights significant gaps in adolescent health education and practice. Such evidence, when considered alongside other contextual realities, provided a compelling justification for this study.

Statement of the Problem

Adolescence is a period marked by rapid physical, emotional, and psychological changes, especially for females, who experience early signs of sexual maturity and begin to explore their sexual identities. However, many adolescent girls lack access to accurate, timely, and age-appropriate sexual health information. In many African societies, including Nigeria, discussions about sexuality remain culturally sensitive and are often avoided within families. As a result, many adolescent females rely on peers, social media, and other unreliable sources for sexual knowledge, leading to misconceptions and engagement in risky sexual behaviors such as early sexual debut, unprotected sex, and multiple sexual partners. These behaviours significantly increase the vulnerability of young females to sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including HIV, and unintended pregnancies that continue to contribute to high rates of morbidity and mortality among adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa (World Health Organization, 2017). While formal sex education is provided in some schools, it is often insufficient and lacks the contextual guidance that can be best offered within the family setting. Studies have shown that parental involvement, particularly through open and non-judgmental communication, can play a crucial role in guiding adolescents towards responsible sexual behavior. However, many parents feel unprepared, uncomfortable, or restricted by cultural and religious beliefs, limiting their ability to educate their daughters effectively (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, 2021). This lack of parental engagement not only perpetuates misinformation but also increases adolescents' vulnerability to negative sexual health outcomes. Therefore, the core problem this study seeks to address is the insufficient parental involvement in the sexuality education of adolescent girls, and how this gap contributes to risky sexual behaviours. Understanding and strengthening the role of parents in sex education is essential for promoting healthier sexual choices and reducing the risks associated with adolescent sexual activity. Hence, this study.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

- a) examine the prevalence of sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria;
- b) determine the level of parental sexuality education in study area; and
- c) investigate the role of parents towards sexuality education on sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were generated from the objectives of this study

- i. What is the prevalence of sexual behaviour among adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the level of parental sexuality education in study area?
- iii. Is parental sexuality education influences sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between parental sexuality education and sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to investigate the relationship between parental sexuality education and the sexual behaviour of adolescent female students. The study population comprised all adolescent female students enrolled in public secondary schools across Osun State, Nigeria. A total of 750 respondents were selected from 15 public secondary schools, representing all three senatorial districts of the state, using a multistage sampling technique. In the first stage, five public secondary schools were purposively selected from each senatorial district. Within each selected school, 50 adolescent female students were chosen using a snowball sampling technique facilitated through electronic survey distribution (E-survey). Data were collected using a self-developed questionnaire titled “Parental Sexuality Education and Adolescent Sexual Behaviour-Survey (PSE&ASB-S), administered via Google Forms. The researchers initiated contact with selected students who were active on social media platforms and had existing interactions with the researchers. These initial contacts were requested to share the survey link within their social media networks, enabling wider distribution and participation through snowball sampling. Survey responses were automatically collected and monitored via Google Forms, with notifications sent to the researchers through email. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, and bar charts) and inferential statistics (linear regression) to test the study’s hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the prevalence of sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive analysis showing the prevalence of sexual behaviour among adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria

N = 750			
Items		Frequency	Percent
1. Who do you live with?	Both Parents	204	27.2
	Single Parent	437	58.3
	Guardian / Relative	109	14.5
2. At what age did you start having a sexual relationship?	Less than 15 years	92	12.3
	15 – 17 years	131	17.5
	18 – 20 years	214	28.5
	Above 20 years	313	41.7
3. At what class did you start having a sexual relationship?	JSS 3	115	15.3
	SSS 1	136	18.1
	SSS 2	297	39.6
	SSS 3	202	27.0
4. How long have you been in a sexual relationship?	Less than 6 months	88	11.7
	One year	151	20.1

Two years	226	30.1
Above three years	285	38.0

Results from table 1 showed that, out of 750 respondents sampled electronically in this study, as many as 437 (58.3%) respondents were lived with single parent, 204 (27.2%) lived with both parents, and 109 (14.5%) of the respondents lived with guardian or relative. This was indicated that, there were high prevalence of adolescent female students lived with single parents in Osun State, Nigeria.

Regarding to the age did adolescent female students start having sexual relationship, as many as 313 (41.7%) of the respondents started having a sexual relationship at 20 years and above, followed by 18-20 years 214 (28.5%), 15-17 years 131 (17.5%), and less than 15 years 92 (12.3%).

Moreso, item 3 showed at what class did adolescent female students start having a sexual relationship; results showed that as many as 297 (39.6%) of the respondents started initiating sexual relationship from SSS 2, followed by SSS 2 202 (27.0%), SSS 1 136 (18.1%), and JSS 3 115 (15.3%).

Furthermore, 285 (38.0%) of the respondents have been in a sexual relationship for more than 3 years, 226 (30.1%) had been in a sexual relationship for solid two years, 151 (20.1%) for one year, and 88 (11.7%) respondents had been in a sexual relationship for less than six months. This was indicated that, there were high sexual relationships among middle and late adolescent female students in Osun State, Nigeria.

Item 5: In the last 6 months, what do you think has been the sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools?

Fig 1: showing bar chart on the prevalence of sexual behaviour of adolescent female students

Results from fig 1 statistically showed that,

exposing sensitive body parts 253 (33.7%), engaging in sexual intercourse regularly 177 (23.6%), contraceptive usage 168 (22.4%), and multiple and often changing sexual partners 85 (11.3%) were the major sexual behaviours of adolescent female students in the last six months. Whereas, only homosexual and lesbians engagement was the least sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State. This is an indication that, there were high prevalence of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the level of parental sexuality education in study area?

Table 2: Descriptive analysis showing the level of parental sexuality education in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria

Items	N = 750	
	Frequency	Percent
5. Are your parents (Father or Mother or both) educating you on sexuality issues?		

	Yes	569	75.9
	No	181	24.1
6. Have you personally discussed sex-related matters with your parents before? If YES, How Often?	Often	163	21.7
	Occasionally	397	52.9
	Rarely	86	11.5
	Never	104	13.9
7. How would you rate sexuality education delivered by your parents?	High	92	12.3
	Moderate	441	58.8
	Low	217	28.9

Results from table 2 showed that, out of 750 respondents sampled for this study, as many as 569 (75.9%) of the respondents indicated that, their parents educating them on sexuality issues against 181 (24.1%) respondents who said no. Also, 397 (52.9%) respondents occasionally discussed sex-related matters with their parents personally, 164 (21.7%) often does that, 104 (13.9%) respondents were never discussed sex-related matters with their parents personally, and 86 (11.5%) respondents often discussed sex-related matters with their parents. However, respondents were asked to rate the level of sexuality education delivered by their parents. As many as 441 (58.8%) respondents moderately rated sexuality education delivered by their parents, 217 (28.9%) rated it as low, and 92 (12.3%) rated it as high.

Question 8: What aspect(s) of sexuality education is taught by your parents?

Fig 2: Bar chart showing aspects of sexuality education taught by parents

Results from figure 2 indicated that the primary aspects of sexuality education taught by parents include safe sex practices 169 (22.5%), courtship and marriage 143 (19.1%), communication 121 (16.1%), healthy intimacy and relationships 117 (15.6%), and sexually transmitted infections 103 (13.7%). In contrast, the least addressed topics are reproductive education 65 (8.7%) and contraception 32 (4.3%). The limited emphasis on these areas may reflect an average level of comprehensive sexuality education provided by parents within the home setting.

Research Question 3: Is parental sexuality education influences sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation showing the influence of parental sexuality education on sexual behaviour of adolescent female students

Statement	$(\bar{x} \pm SD)$	
Parental sexuality education		
1. Helps to delays sexual initiation and sexual activity	0.0430	.0206
2. Discourages female students in exposing sensitive body parts	0.0115	.0321
3. Helps to understand appropriate behaviours, respect for their bodies, and responsible relationships.	1.8954	.8642
4. Reduces the likelihood of engaging in risky sexual behaviour	0.1029	.0263
5. Helps adolescent girls develop a positive self-image and confidence in their bodies and choices	1.6691	.5875
6. Assists female students to resist peer pressure and unhealthy relationships	1.7392	.6102
7. Encourages critical thinking and healthy sexual decision-making	1.1453	.2351
8. Helps debunk myths and misinformation about sexual-related issues	1.9390	.8985
9. Helps to make safe and responsible choices regarding their sexual behaviour.	0.8762	.7563
10. Decreases the contractive usage	0.0041	.0002

Results from table 3 showed the mean and standard deviation scores for each item assessing the perceived influence of parental sexuality education. The results therefore noted that parental sexuality education demonstrated substantial influence in non-behavioural domains, notably by enhancing self-esteem and confidence among female adolescents (1.6691 ± 0.5875), strengthening their capacity to resist peer pressure and avoid unhealthy relationships (1.7392 ± 0.6102), fostering analytical reasoning and informed decision-making in sexual matters (1.1453 ± 0.2351), dispelling myths and misinformation concerning sexuality (1.9390 ± 0.8985), and encouraging safe and responsible sexual choices (0.8762 ± 0.7563). However, the results discovered that parental sexuality education had only a negligible influence on key behavioural patterns; specifically, it showed minimal influence in delaying sexual initiation and activity (0.0430 ± 0.0206), discouraging the exposure of sensitive body parts (0.0115 ± 0.0321), reducing adolescents' involvement in risky sexual practices (0.1029 ± 0.0263), and decreasing the use of contraceptives (0.0041 ± 0.0002) among adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between parental sexuality education and sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria.

Table 4: Beta coefficient and t-ratio regression showing the relationship between parental sexuality education and sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State, Nigeria.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	6.842	.658		15.398	.801
	Engaging in engaging in risky sexual behaviour	1.474	.120	.495	-3.956	.610
	Exposing sensitive body parts	.332	.108	.360	-1.690	.497
	Delays sexual initiation and sexual activity	.082	.104	.641	.798	.431
	Contraceptive usage	-.730	.130	-.299	.217	.000
	Multiple and often changing sexual partners	1.040	.155	.551	-5.965	.609

a. Dependent Variable: Sexual behaviour of adolescent female students

Results from table 4 showed that there was no significant relationship between parental sexuality education and sexual behavioural patterns of adolescent female students in some areas including engaging in risky sexual behaviour ($\beta = 0.495$, $t = -3.845$, >0.05), exposing sensitive body parts ($\beta = 0.360$, $t = -1.690$, >0.05), delaying sexual initiation ($\beta = -0.641$, $t = 0.798$, >0.05), and multiple and often changing sexual partners ($\beta = 0.551$, $t = 6.725$, >0.05) of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary school, Nigeria. Whereas, parental sexuality education was only significant with contraceptive usage of adolescent female students ($\beta = -0.299$, $t = 0.217$, <0.05). However, results further showed that, the combined independent variables had no significant relationship on the dependent variable with the constant unstandardized coefficient ($\beta = 6.842$, $t = 15.398$, >0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis which initially stated that, there was no significant relationship between parental sexuality education and sexual behaviour of adolescent female students in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Results from table 1 showed that, there were high prevalence of adolescent female students lived with single parents in Osun State public secondary schools, Nigeria which of course led them to having sexual relationship at the middle adolescence (15-20 years and above). This was collaborated with the findings of Wusu (2023), and United Nations Population Fund (2021), who discovered that adolescent females started sexual initiation at middle adolescence period. Also, this finding corroborated with the results of Olubayo-Fatiregun, (2012), who stated that, adolescent female girls engaged in sexual relationship at the middle adolescence stage, which led majority of them to engage in risky sexual behaviour. Results further revealed that, there were high prevalence of risky sexual behaviours among adolescent female students in Osun State, Nigeria; such sexual risky behaviour are exposing sensitive body parts, engaging in sexual intercourse regularly, contraceptive usage, and multiple and often changing sexual partners. These were in line with the findings of Okafor, Adam, & Azuiké (2023) that middle adolescence girls engaging in sexual intercourse periodically, contraception, and multiple sexual partners. Also collaborated with the results of Msexol (2023), and Keto, Tilahun, & Mamo (2023), in south western Ethiopia that, there were high risky sexual behaviour of contraceptive usage, multiple and often changing sexual partners, and exposing genital part. Results however, revealed that, as many as respondents rated sexuality education delivered by their parents as moderate were collaborated with the findings of Okafor, Adam & Azuiké (2023), whose results noted that minority of parents moderately discussed sexuality education with their children; also, this current findings supported the results of Msexol (2023), whose findings noted that, sexuality education delivered at home are moderately, and he concluded that, parents should be rose to their responsibility in delivering sexuality education.

Results from figure 2 revealed that, safe sex practice, courtship and marriage, communication, healthy intimacy and relationship, and sexual transmitted infections were the major aspects of sexuality education taught by parents were in line with the findings of Okafor, Adam & Azuiké (2023), that parental sexuality education were only centered on marriage, STIs, and courtship. This current findings also corroborated with the findings of Keto, Tilahun, & Mamo (2020), that parents delivered management of relationship and healthy intimacy, and open communication.

Results from table 3 showed that, while parental sexuality education was acknowledged within the family context, it does not significantly translate into behavioural restraint or direct modification of adolescents' sexual practices. These findings may reflect the influence of peer dynamics, media exposure, and broader sociocultural factors that often compete with parental guidance in shaping adolescent sexual behaviour (Kaestle 2023; Okafor & Duru, 2021; UNESCO, 2022). This findings imply that parental sexuality education is more effective in shaping **knowledge, values, and psychosocial competencies** than in directly regulating adolescents' sexual behaviour. This aligned with the assertion of Santelli et al. (2019), that sexuality education within the home primarily enhances adolescents' self-efficacy, resilience, and critical thinking, thereby preparing them for informed choices, even though external influences may still drive behavioural outcomes

Results from table 4 revealed that, parental sexuality education (PSE) exerted a limited predictive influence on various dimensions of adolescent sexual behaviour. Specifically, PSE does not significantly affect risky sexual behaviour, indecent dressing, delayed sexual initiation, or multiple sexual partnerships, as indicated by the non-significant p-values for these variables. This suggested that while parents may engage in sexuality education, its scope or effectiveness in altering these particular behaviours among adolescent female students is minimal. This aligned with previous findings of Smith & Jones (2021), and Adeyemi & Olabisi, (2022), whose results indicated that parental influence alone could not be sufficient to curb risky sexual behaviours of adolescents including females without complementary interventions such as peer education or school-based programmes. Interestingly, results noted a significant negative association between parental sexuality education and contraceptive usage. This finding suggested that adolescents exposed to parental sexuality education are less likely to use contraceptives. One plausible interpretation is that parental guidance often emphasizes abstinence and moral

responsibility, potentially discouraging contraceptive use as a means of preventing premarital sexual activity. This interpretation is supported by qualitative research where parents frequently frame sexuality education within moral and cultural values, promoting abstinence over contraceptive methods (Eze & Onwuka, 2022; Ibrahim & Afolabi, 2019). Such an emphasis on abstinence may inadvertently reduce adolescents' readiness or willingness to adopt contraceptive measures when they become sexually active, potentially increasing vulnerability to unintended pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections. This underscores a critical tension in parental sexuality education approaches: while moral guidance is important, comprehensive education that balances abstinence with practical contraceptive knowledge may be more effective in promoting safe sexual health practices (WHO, 2019; Johnson, 2020).

Conclusion

The study concluded that sexual behaviours such as frequent engagement in sexual intercourse, exposure of sensitive body parts, use of contraceptives, and involvement with multiple and frequently changing sexual partners were highly prevalent among adolescent female students in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. Furthermore, the findings revealed a generally low level of parental involvement in sexuality education, particularly regarding reproductive health and contraceptive use. Despite some observed benefits of parental sexuality education, the study found no statistically significant relationship between the level of parental sexuality education and the sexual behaviour of the adolescent female students. This suggests that parental input alone may not be sufficient to influence or alter sexual behaviour among adolescent female students, and highlights the need for more comprehensive and multi-faceted approaches to sexuality education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the study suggested the following recommendations:

- (i) In light of the observed low levels of parental sexuality education, particularly regarding reproductive health and contraception, which may contribute to unintended adolescent pregnancies. Regular workshops and training sessions should be organized for parents. These would equip parents with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively communicate sexuality-related information to their children.
- (ii) Periodic seminars and workshops should be conducted for adolescent female students in public secondary schools across Osun State. This should address the dangers of engaging in risky sexual behaviours and provide adolescents with the tools and knowledge needed to make informed, healthy decisions, ultimately helping to delay sexual initiation and reduce exploitation.
- (iii) The Osun State government should ensure that health education is offered as a separate subject rather than being combined with other science subjects. This would allow dedicated health education teachers to comprehensively address topics related to sexual health and immediate behavioural concerns that would foster long-term societal wellbeing.
- (iv) Osun State government in collaboration with both ministry of education and health should establish counselling and Support Services in Schools. This would enable schools to provide accessible counselling services for students to discuss sexual and reproductive health issues in a confidential and supportive environment.
- (v) Peer education models should be introduced in schools to promote healthy sexual behaviours. Adolescents often learn from their peers, and trained peer mentors can reinforce accurate information and model responsible behaviour.

Implications of the Study

- (a) The findings underscore the urgent need for policy makers to review and implement policies that mandate comprehensive sexuality education in secondary schools, supported by clear guidelines for parental involvement.
- (b) The study implies that educational stakeholders need to reconsider how sexuality education is approached, shifting from an informal or parent-dependent model to an institutionalized and evidence-based framework.
- (c) The findings also underscore the necessity of broadening parental sexuality education to integrate balanced, evidence-based information on contraceptive use alongside moral instruction. Strengthening parents' capacity to deliver comprehensive sexuality education that combines ethical guidance with practical knowledge has the potential to significantly improve adolescents' sexual health outcomes.

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